

RESEARCH PAPER

" AI AND ARCHITECTURE TO PREVENT CRIMES IN NEGLECTED SPACES"

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Abstract:

This article examines the relationship between Architecture and Ai to prevent crime in neglected spaces. The demand for cities and metropolitan areas is skyrocketing nowadays. However, many urban cores have vast swaths of underutilized real estate, sometimes called "Neglected Spaces." They need to pay more attention to the potential loss of places together with their original placement, original residents, and original worth. Therefore, these abandoned areas are likely to become a hotbed for criminal activity, endangering the safety of new residents and tourists. By using the power of Ai that in these years it is getting more and more updated and useful and interventional architecture thoughts, we can get the security of people to high rates and lower the criminal activities in that areas or even finish it. We can make abandoned neighborhoods safer and more secure by fusing criminological insights, creative architectural redesign, and smart city security systems. We can make abandoned areas safer and more secure by connecting criminological insights, innovative architectural redesign, and smart city security systems. In this article, we will examine the Ai role in surveillance systems, the use of smart lighting to prevent crime, and the joining point of these technologies in smart cities. Neglected regions may become prosperous, safe, and secure places using a complete strategy that blends criminology, architecture, and AI.

Keywords: Neglected spaces, Criminology, Redesign, smart lighting, smart city security

Introduction:

First, mixing Ai and Architecture comes to the author's mind when watching the minority report movie and then seeing that Ai is growing. The architectures need to use these Ai technologies in their design and even in their product, from designing a home with Ai to building this area. Then because of the poverty in the city, neglected places will become more in the towns. They harm people's safety, so the author decided to work on this topic. Neglected areas present unique safety and security challenges, frequently linked with high crime rates, social instability, and urban decay. Addressing these issues necessitates novel strategies that utilize the power of artificial intelligence and architectural redesign. By incorporating criminological insights and leveraging the capabilities of intelligent technologies, abandoned spaces can be transformed into more secure and peaceful environments. This article examines the potential for AI and architecture to prevent crime in neglected spaces, focusing on "Neglected spaces, Criminology, Smart lighting, and Smart city security." Multiple variables define neglected spaces, including physical decline, limited monitoring, and an absence of social cohesion. These areas frequently become hubs for illicit activity, causing residents to feel unsafe and discouraging potential investors. Utilizing criminology, architecture, and technology, a multidisciplinary strategy is required to resolve these challenges. On the other hand, looking at the negative points of using ai and architecture and what will happen if it is used in the wrong direction is essential.

Criminology:

Criminology offers invaluable knowledge of the causes of crime and the trends of criminal conduct. Architects and designers can integrate this understanding into the redesigning procedure if they comprehend the root causes and dynamics of illicit activities in neglected spaces. Criminological studies help identify crime centers, regions of focus, and populations at risk, thereby facilitating the creation of effective measures to prevent offenses and improve community safety. Redesigning architecture plays a crucial role in converting abandoned spaces into secure environments. Using the concepts of Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED), architects can design environments that deter illicit activity and encourage positive interactions among people. Redesign efforts may involve structural alterations, entry control, illumination, and incorporating parts of natural monitoring. For instance, the careful positioning of illumination fixtures can increase accessibility and discourage possible perpetrators, thereby making abandoned areas less alluring for criminal activity.

In addition, the development of intelligent technologies such as artificial intelligence and smart lighting gives new prospects for preventing crime in areas that have been overlooked. Real-time surveillance, predictive analytics, and clever reaction mechanisms are all made possible by surveillance systems driven by artificial intelligence. These systems can identify suspicious activity, detect abnormalities, and offer timely notifications to law enforcement authorities because they use artificial intelligence (AI) capabilities. By dynamically altering lighting levels

depending on use patterns and current environmental circumstances, smart lighting, on the other hand, increases visibility, raises safety standards, and instills a feeling of safety and security in the surrounding area. (1) Eventually, quality of life will decrease, making people seek their needs through illegal acts.

Figure 1. Defining serious and organized crime. (1)

Neglected spaces: Safe Haven for crime

"Neglected spaces" refers to locations disregarded or ignored by the larger society. Neglected areas allow criminals to commit crimes without fear of being caught; hence, they often target these areas. Because of these areas' protection and secrecy, it is difficult for law enforcement organizations to keep track of illegal activities in these areas. They provide a dangerous and unwelcoming atmosphere, which may lead to a lack of social interaction and more neglect. It is critical to acknowledge this problem's gravity and take steps to mitigate the risk of criminal activity in unused public areas.

Disadvantages of Neglected Spaces:

Urban areas are in high demand these days. Despite this, many urban cores have vast swaths of underutilized land known as "Neglected Spaces." Spaces that may have been abandoned through time, the people who used them, and the importance they formerly had, have been mostly disregarded. As a result, the safety of new residents and visitors to these areas will likely be compromised as these unused areas become magnets for criminal activity.

Redesigning Neglected Spaces for Safety:

There are several factors, such as Locations, redesigning neglected areas to make them safer depending on where they are located and the crimes that frequently occur there. Secondly

Improved Accessibility, we can increase the number of individuals in the neighborhood by making the place more accessible, which will result in fewer opportunities for criminal activity. Thirdly Designing for Visibility, it is possible to make the area very highly illuminated; this, together with other reasons, discourages illegal activity by making it more obvious to others around them; assigning new purposes to spaces is beneficial because it gives such spaces meaning and draws in visitors who are more likely to feel invested in the experiences on offer. Provide a less risky setting by doing away with any potential hazards. Visitors won't have to worry as much about their safety, and the abandoned land will finally be put to good use. It catered to the wishes of the general public. Based on that analysis, this may be done by examining the site and adjusting to users' unique needs and preferences. The aesthetic value of the city is raised as a result. If there aren't already enough parks or other public places, this may be a great place to put one. Having a central meeting place for each cluster of buildings is crucial because it may significantly reduce the amount of foot traffic in the main public space of the district. Promote vegetation and create parks and pocket parks where there are none. This will raise the oxygen standard and provide a soothing environment for the consumers.

Smart cities:

Smart city security is the best way to prevent crime in neglected spaces. By using technology, people community engagement, and using the law, we can design and create safe places and environments for people. Security of the smart city will provide by sensors, CCTV cameras, and other technologies for monitoring criminal activity. Governors can use these data to set the law enforcement in that area and provide crime from happening in that location. And additionally, some programs between law enforcement and the community living there can share responsibility for safety and security.

The Role of Smart City Security in Crime Prevention:

Enhanced Surveillance in smart cities, surveillance systems can monitor potential hotspots and immediately notify authorities of any unusual activity. Rapid Response, Quicker police or emergency response times made possible by smart city design may reduce reaction times to crime and other situations. Effective Crime Prevention, The effectiveness of crime prevention may be improved with the use of smart city security technologies for detecting and discouraging offenders.

Surveillance and privacy concerns:

The use of surveillance technology in neglected spaces is making some concerns about people's privacy and freedom of people. While we know that Ai and smart technology are perfect and practical tools for preventing crime, fixing these benefits with the community's needs is essential. To solve these concerns, it is vital to maintain flawless and solid laws and guidelines to answer the people. To fight and stop these criminal acts and make a difference, tackling the causes of social inequality is essential. Furthermore, the use of architecture and Ai might increase

social inequality by changing the location of the crime to neighboring spaces because of the lack of surveillance and protection in the places that can cause changes to the areas that are not neglected but are safe from criminal activities.

Limited effectiveness:

An AI system for reading the data analysis to identify and predict criminal behavior of people. However, in neglected spaces, we have a lack of data about the crime happening, which makes data analysis for AI harder. Limited access to data and even the old data of that space make the AI ineffective in preventing crimes. Secondly, architectural measures about lighting, surveillance cameras, and urban design will help to prevent crime. However, using these options in the neglected areas because of the need for more money and expenses and infrastructure support makes it more challenging. Neglected spaces become neglected because of a lack of money or material, and even repairing stretches will make the job of architecture harder. When AI and architectural options were applied to the neglected areas, they would be changeable and limited by the dynamic changes in criminal behavior. Criminals can adapt to the site and their behavioral response to preventive measures, making the interventions less effective in the time. Additionally, changing the place from one neglected area to another one is what is happening routinely, indicating solid and programmable approaches to the factories of crime prevention.

Social Inequality:

Neglected spaces because of the inequity that is happening between the city that is living in that and other areas are happening. People in these areas, in some cases, are the people who are socially and economically disadvantaged. Therefore, in these cases, some don't have anyway but only act in these criminal activities for a living. By improving smart lighting technologies, monitoring systems, and upgrading some other safety measures, AI and architecture can help improve the area to prevent crime in neglected spaces. These changes make the gaps between neighborhoods, keep poverty and corruption in their place, and even strengthen them. Artificial intelligence and building design might significantly contribute to crime prevention in these areas by enhancing lighting, surveillance, and other safety measures.

Technological Limitation:

AI and well-designed buildings by architecture may prevent crime in neglected spaces, so should take action in technical construction. For example, for more reliable references and true judgments, AI needs to waste a variety of data and update that data every day. In the areas where this theology or materials are low, there will need to be more data to train the system and update it. In this case, we have a gut problem with misconduct in information about crime prevention or false alarms about it happening and cannot stop it. Adding more technology to people's life concerns privacy and civil liberties. More surveillance and monitoring may cause people to become angrier and not respect the governors. It shows that we need to make AI use of

Architecture to balance people's lives between making technology and updating and making people safer and violating their privacy.

Neglected Root Causes:

AI systems depend substantially on data input to make correct predictions and conclusions. However, in regions with limited access to technology and resources, there may need to be more data available to train these systems adequately. This might lead to erroneous or biased predictions, which can result in false alarms or the loss of chances to prevent criminal activity. In addition, introducing sophisticated surveillance technology might raise issues over individuals' rights to privacy and other civil freedoms.

Displacement of Crime:

Although mixing Ai and Architecture can lower crime in neglected areas, it can only change crime from one place to another. Concentrating on crime prevention in neglected spaces is essential, but we should focus on the possibility of immigration and relocation of these criminal acts. Consequently, similar precautions must be taken over far greater areas to stop the simple movement of illegal activity.

Smart Lighting and its Impact:

Smart lighting, a based-on technology solution, has tremendously affected architecture, presenting the new potential for enriching spatial experiences and reshaping built spaces. This has resulted in an expansion of the architectural design space. Smart lighting has evolved as a potent tool that can be used to create dynamic, energy-efficient, and aesthetically attractive architectural settings. This is in addition to its functional elements. This article examines the influence of smart lighting on architecture, concentrating on its advantages, design issues, and future ramifications for the industry's trajectory in the years to come.

Case study:

. Akaretler District in Istanbul:

Akaretler is a district located in the city of Istanbul, Turkey. It consisted of a collection of row houses which are located on the intersection of the Şair Nedim and Süleyman Seba streets in the Beşiktaş district. Due to its central location and historical heritage, Akaretler is considered an area with huge potential.

By the beginning of the 1980s, according to Ronael & Oruç (2019), Akaretler had faced many physical and social issues; the inhabitants and users felt unsafe as it lacked safety and security. Therefore, the Ministry of Culture and Tourism suggested a new plan to restore row houses (Milliyet Newspaper, 1980).

The reconstruction project underwent several changes due to continuous changes in the requirements. Still, in the end, the area has witnessed a radical transformation as it has been converted into an art and design district.

Akaretler row houses before and after restoration. (Bilgili Holding)

Inhabitants who lived in the area for more than 30 years have confirmed that the restoration has successfully changed the visual quality of the district and Istanbul as a city. They were also pleased with how their own properties have been positively affected. Inhabitants feel safe as they walk through the high-quality streets of Akaretler with glancing and eye-catching lights used to make building facades more beautiful and get the people to move in the road and go inside the restaurants and bars. Still, these can not only make the place safer or protectable, they use guards outside of the area but did anybody think about it after the restaurants closed?

At present, the buildings that housed stores and boutiques are now home to upscale eateries and trendy hangout spots for artists. Visitors from all across Istanbul, including those with higher disposable incomes, may currently be found in this region.

Benefits of Smart Lighting in Architecture:

Adaptive lighting solutions contribute to both energy efficiency and environmental sustainability. Creating dynamic lighting situations requires a degree of flexibility and agility. They are increasing the productivity, comfort, and overall well-being of the occupants—aesthetics of appearance and the alteration of spatial configurations in architecture. Programmable lighting controls enable concerns for personal safety and property protection.

A Brighter Future, Smart lighting systems use sensors to make automated adjustments to the amount of lighting, increasing visibility and making the place more aesthetically pleasing.
Improved Safety, Smart lighting systems use sensors to make automatic adjustments to the amount of illumination, increasing visibility and making the area more aesthetically pleasing.

The Dark Side of Smart Lighting:

Increasing reliance from humankind on smart lighting has several dark aspects of view for this technology. One of the concerns is the vulnerability of smart lighting against cyber-attacks and hackers because this system has become more usable. There are some back doors for hackers to reach the applications, compromising users' privacy and security. Malvers can go to the system and, by fully controlling the lighting or even getting access to other devices that are in contact with the smart lighting system, can harm or do threatening actions against humans. Moreover, depending more on these systems can lead to losing control and autonomy; for example, when there is a power outage, or lights go off, the user finds out that they cannot do anything manually to control it. This can make people more hopeless and have psychological effects. By the way, using these technologies will have expenses for maintenance and even higher costs for upgrading them or adding new systems to them, and they need technical experts too. Another concern is the impact of using smart lighting on the environment. All places or companies are saying that these products use for sustainable use. Still, producing these technologies requires a high number of resources, including rare earth materials for production, and even destroying these technologies after they get used will harm the planet. Limited Effectiveness is one of the reasons. Although smart lighting may effectively reduce crime, it cannot do so everywhere. Furthermore, by adding smart lighting to our daily lives, we give access to applications to get out data and store usage patterns and user preferences; if these data are not secure good, these dates can raise concerns about data security and lead to breaches.

While smart lighting has good help to people and using electric power but relying on the technology raises concerns about cybersecurity, loss of control of the devices, environmental impacts, and data privacy. Looking to the darker side of smart lighting and fixing these problems in the future can be helpful for the users to use it more.

Combining Modern Technology with Timeless Architecture:

The use of intelligent lighting in innovative building systems, the importance of lighting in the construction of buildings, and the effect that lighting has on people's experiences, The development of lighting technology, including the transition from conventional to advanced lighting systems.

Conclusion:

Integrating artificial intelligence, architectural design, and criminological theory offers a potentially helpful paradigm for suppressing criminal activity in underutilized areas. Neglected areas may be made safer and more secure by integrating criminological information into the design process, applying architectural redesign tactics, and leveraging innovative technology such as artificial intelligence and smart lighting. This comprehensive strategy, which is supported by cooperation between experts from many fields, can revive neglected regions, enhance community well-being, and enable the growth of urban ecosystems that are robust. Understanding the mechanics of crime, as revealed by criminology, may be helpful for architects and designers throughout the redesign process. Architectural modifications guided by CPTED principles may reduce opportunities for criminal behavior while increasing opportunities for lawful social engagement. Real-time monitoring, predictive analytics, and prompt reaction mechanisms are all made possible by AI-powered surveillance systems and smart lighting technologies, further strengthening safety precautions. Although artificial intelligence (AI) and building design may help reduce crime, there are still specific issues to work out. To ensure that technological progress serves the interests and ideals of the community, it is vital to handle concerns about privacy and the possibility of social inequity. The dynamic nature of criminal conduct presents problems with sustaining long-term efficiency, and limited access to data and resources in ignored places may impair the effectiveness of AI systems. By looking at all the options that Ai and Architecture would face in the future, we can see that Ai has a wide variety for examination and need to become more secure by mixing it with architecture again security and privacy of the dwellers are more critical. So, new things like Ai technologies will have problems for people that should be fixed, and it shows that it is possible to use Ai and Architecture together to prevent crime in neglected spaces. Still, it needs the governor's help and should secure people's privacy too.

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